

SSHOC

social sciences & humanities open cloud

SSHOC Project Brief

To support the EC Programme
and policy activities

Abstract

SSHOC Thematic cluster project [2019-2022] has built a strong and recognisable brand around a consortium of **6 well-established ESFRIs, 7 onboarded Social Science and Humanities (SSH) data communities, an SSH Open Marketplace testers' community and an SSH Training Community** actively breaking down the silos through the sharing of knowledge, tools and services with significant potential for further capacity-building as an important building block for EOSC.

Through a solid and continued outreach programme it has engaged over 5000 stakeholders in 65+ events organised, with a social media community of 2200+ members, and 470 newsletter subscribers.

Niche scientific communities have been supported by providing 6 additional targeted training events offering a valuable platform to support the onboarding of new communities to present themselves as well as to connect their members from all over the world. The SSHOC website acts as a main communication channel and is the gateway to its array of services including the **SSH catalogue of services**, connecting its 60+ official reports to each single Key Exploitable Result (KERs) actively consulted by the SSH community (i.e. the System Specification of the SSH Open Marketplace has been downloaded over 4300 times).

With the release in December 2021 of the EU Data Governance Act, SSHOC pursues the regulations around the guiding principles of the act to support a Data Science ecosystem in the area of SSH.

1. Integration with the EOSC infrastructure

(a) main results achieved so far

Integration of Discipline-centric Services The integration with the EOSC infrastructure was done by onboarding the thematic services developed, extended, or used in SSHOC to the EOSC catalogue of services. SSHOC succeeded in developing web-based tools and testing new data production methodologies to assist the collection of high-quality cross-national and multilingual data (e.g. survey data, social media data, historical letters, political records) and metadata in a cost-effective and streamlined way. The aim is to advance experimentation and tools to promote the transition from a heavily human-based annotation and translation workflow enabling comparative research, to one that is technology driven, with a high emphasis on the use of text analytics and machine translation.

Capacity Building and User Integration SSHOC actively onboards end-users via dedicated calls (e.g., Applications for SSHOC Repository Certification Support), tailored events (e.g., workshop on the agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace), and user success stories. **Technical Integration** - SSH Open Marketplace & EOSC integration has been realised and implemented. It assumes integration of the EOSC Core service (the EOSC AAI). (Re)-use of the SSH part of the EOSC catalogue is intended to populate the Marketplace. Collection of around 5000 items of interest for digital methods in SSH are listed there. In addition, the tools developed within SSHOC will be added to the SSHOC Marketplace. Information about the SSHOC Marketplace is shared with non-SSHOC members of the data communities i.e. the process to onboard the EMM Survey Registry to EOSC Portal has started, with in-kind support by the regional project "EOSC Pillar".

33 SHOCing Key Exploitable Results to support your research in SSH and Beyond

(b) expected developments by the end of the project

The community activated by SSHOC is expanding and aims to be the reference point in Europe for SSH research resources long after the project finishes. The consortium is transforming the SSHOC project branding into sustainable branding for all KERs, leveraging on the strong visual identity of the project and keeping the door open for new communities to join - "the SSH Open Cluster" and "Social Sciences and Humanities Research Resources" through its MoU it has defined for future cooperation opportunities.

EOSC infrastructure integration activities mentioned under (a) will be concluded. It is expected to have created and entered into lasting collaborations with the other SSH stakeholders, (e.g. the SSH Vocabulary Commons). KERs will be finalised to support research and data in the SSH, The WPSS (Web Panel Sample System), the MCSQ (Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires), the SSHOCro and the Aioli platform, League of Data platform, to name a few. A number of expected developments will allow existing and new data users to be the main beneficiaries of the upgraded data management and dissemination tools.

More outreach events on secondary data management and data sharing are expected. The SSH Open Marketplace will prioritise its position on EOSC service catalogue onboarding. The image below provides an inclusive view of the KERs developed within SSHOC and differentiates the service offering through specific SSH and KERs that may be adopted by other multi-disciplinary communities.

(c) recommendations on follow-up priorities linked to the further development of EOSC

Facilitate further collaboration in the SSH community regarding alignment of data, services and interoperability solutions, and sharing of (thematic) services in EOSC. Leveraging the already activated thematic data communities would be of great benefit, including the expert support that has enabled smaller communities to become frontrunners in the digital transition, mobilising users, and highlighting the valuable resources (e.g. training), to connect to Data Spaces.

Work with communities to realise systemic **EOSC awareness** and provide long-term support to sustain and engage research communities actively involved in data management projects.

Extend EOSC Core to provide infrastructure services flexible enough to accommodate specific community requirements, including alignment with community governance. It includes the incorporation of the SSH Open Marketplace resources with the nascent EOSC catalogue as well as support the maintenance of tools, and agile adaptation to rapid technology changes.

Foster interdisciplinary initiatives to allow target groups to exploit the data to its full potential, showcasing tools and services with use-cases crossing the domain borders. Harmonisation of practice in handling data protection in research is also needed.

2. FAIR principles implementation and repositories

(a) main results achieved so far

SSHOC actively applied FAIR principles in the planning of data products, such as vocabularies and ontologies; produced easy-to-use recommendations for data citation in SSH domains; investigated SSH interoperability challenges, and produced recommendations. To ensure reusability of outputs, in data production innovations, a special focus was put on licences. Tools supporting FAIR data were designed or improved, such as [Web panel sample system](#) (compliant with GDPR, a necessity for survey projects which allows the production of FAIR data), [Multilingual corpus of survey questionnaires \(MCSO\)](#) (FAIR by design, improving translation procedures and data quality), [EMM Survey registry](#) (enriched with cross-disciplinary take on including FAIR data citation principles, use of PIDs and DDI as a standard for interoperable data), or [SSH Training Discovery Toolkit](#) covering several curated topics relating to FAIR principles, to name a few.

[The SSH Open Marketplace](#) is designed to support the uptake of FAIR principles by referencing, enriching, and collecting useful resources to upgrade digital methods used in the SSH. As a discovery platform, it supports findability and reusability of resources. SSHOC also established a program for SSH repositories to become **Trusted Digital Repositories** via CoreTrustSeal certification, adopting standards and FAIR principles. This also credits a successful collaboration and alignment with FAIRsFAIR and EOSC Nordic projects in developing best practises and clarifying the trust landscape.

(b) expected developments by the end of the project

SSHOC will be publishing all data results according to FAIR principles: multilingual vocabularies and ontologies, SSH vocabulary platform, conversion solutions etc. A FAIR SSH citation prototype will allow gathering standardised information about datasets from different sources, giving visibility to both research products (datasets) and repositories, eventually enhancing their FAIRness.

SSHOC will finalise tools and services being developed, as well as continue onboarding FAIR tools and services to EOSC and including

them in the SSH Marketplace, providing recommendations for FAIR compliance where possible. This will allow other communities to use them, improving their data practises.

All SSHOC reports will be published in [Zenodo](#) and widely promoted. FAIR data sets will be produced with recommendations and examples of resources, and metadata requirements. Datasets linked to training materials, tools, workflows will be enhanced, increasing their accessibility, interoperability, and reuse. SSHOC will provide recommendations for sustainably maintaining trust across the SSH ERICs beyond the lifetime of the SSHOC project.

(c) recommendations on follow-up priorities linked to the further development of EOSC

Support efficient and aligned **quality evaluation** contributing to the added value of all discovery tools, catalogues, registries for end-users and end-user infrastructure, with a special focus on possible overlap and quality issues risking fragmentation and documentation debris. Providing resources for repositories to upgrade operations to required certified levels (CTS) is recommended, as well as encouraging collaboration or merging into larger facilities to provide FAIR high-quality (meta)data, curation, and guaranteed access.

Promote **cross-disciplinary/domain standards** as a baseline and disciplinary/domain specialities where necessary. In a FAIR ecosystem, there should be Trustworthy Metadata Repositories criteria similar to the CoreTrustSeal for TDR data repositories.

Embed **FAIR Awareness**. The EC should foresee stabilising funding streams to raise awareness and implications of the FAIR principles in daily research undertaking. A range of funded schemes for 'ambassadors', instead of current volunteering, is suggested. Concretely, instruments similar to the 'Jean Monnet Chairs' funding scheme to promote the study of EU/European issues, but focusing on Open Science and FAIR research would likely be an effective way to reach throughout all Europe via on-the-ground initiatives.

3. Technical, semantic, legal, and organisational interoperability

(a) main results achieved so far

SSHOC delivered the inventory of SSH (meta) data solutions, Conversion Hub and conversion solutions, and started “SSH vocabulary commons”. The FAIR SSH citation prototype provides technical and semantic interoperability. Furthermore, licences are adopted for data and tools that promote reuse and sustainability (Data communities’ first tools are licensed). GDPR compliant tools have been constructed to improve the management of data collection lifecycles (WPSS).

The service allowing heritage researchers to document historical artefacts in a FAIR way (Aïoli), “Archive in the box solution”, and additional Dataverse functionalities were developed. CIDOC-CRM ontology and semantic modelling approach were used and data storage in the same structure is supported. API harvesting and search functions were integrated in tools.

A flexible data model of the SSH Open Marketplace that enables large (meta)data collection, processing, and curation across SSH domains was established and allows inclusion of low metadata quality resources. SSHOC also delivered Guidelines to streamline data production processes of several survey projects at the same time, a draft SSH GDPR Code of Conduct and a framework for Data Use Agreements.

(b) expected developments by the end of the project

SSH Vocabulary Commons collaboration aimed at SSH vocabulary management alignment will continue. Dataverse developments will be finalised and integrated in the Harvard master branch. Schema for categorising and assigning disclosure risk levels to data collections and completion of the bilateral secure connection with a model and resources will be provided.

SSHOC delivery of the **SSH Open Marketplace**. It will provide a sustainable overview of the service offer resulting from the project. Marketplace will set up an Editorial Board to ensure continuous update, guarantee data quality standards in the MP and community management around SSH resources. Data communities will be dealing with the expansion of use of the DDI metadata standard through adoption by data communities directly and connection with other national-level aggregators.

Finalisation of the SSH GDPR Code of Conduct is planned by the end of the project.

(c) recommendations on follow-up priorities linked to the further development of EOSC

Legal framework Support for formalisation of clusters’ internal cooperation links (e.g. the SSH Open Cluster MoU) as an umbrella framework allowing a common approach to outputs (SSHOC KERs) focusing on sustainability and investment of keeping those tools and services up to date.

Resolve the issues of **Remote Access to Sensitive Data** The main priority for EOSC will be to develop and sustain an infrastructure with the capacity to provide access to data types that are of a sensitive character (e.g. patient data, personal interview recordings). The SSHOC 2021 White paper will provide recommendations, however, given challenges related to such facilities in terms of creation and operation, a strong and long-term commitment is needed as an incentive for investments, both for individual countries and/or RIs.

Ensure **rewards and incentives** for professionals involved in data collection and curation for the benefits of the whole community. Thematic services are the main guarantee for end-user uptake, especially in cross-domain research settings. state-of-the-art

Fully integrate the **science Clusters** and their state-of-the-art into EOSC planning and development. In the light of the nascent new SRIA/MAR, where both community update and the engagement of ‘non-obvious disciplines’ such as SSH are priority areas, further considerable investments in the technology stack used in SSHOC and other clusters will be required in order to maintain the cutting-edge status of tools and services provided to EOSC.

Create Effective SSH User Stories via different target groups to help draw a diverse and larger set of target groups towards EOSC (i.e.: from the research community, academia, SMEs or large industry) the SSH community may collect and experiment with a set of user stories through storytelling which target group carries out a specific objective and goal.

4. Stewardship of data

(a) main results achieved so far

SSHOC collected and curated training materials' workflows and (meta)data, addressing data stewardship topics in SSH. The [SSH Training Discovery Toolkit](#) covers several curated topics related to data stewardship. The [Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps](#) contributed to data stewardship training, including a dedicated [Bootcamp for Librarians](#) (including data stewards). The [SSH Training Community](#) (currently at 170+ people) organised discussions on topics related to data stewardship.

Other results include: SSH data citation recommendations, Web Panel Sample System and Aioli Platform tools (both provide a FAIR solution to data stewardship - one supporting the management of data collection, and the other data collection in a harmonised FAIR way); [series of webinars](#) on Dataverse as a long-term perseverance solution held, as well as EMM survey registry webinar for researchers to onboard their surveys, policy for use, training videos, plus data quality control process documentation was held. [Training materials](#) for Secure Data Facility professionals were produced. SSH Open Marketplace contributes to data stewardship by describing/referencing clear provenance trails and clear contributor roles, ensuring role recognition along the data lifecycle. SSHOC has recognised the need and value of data stewardship in the *Certification plan for SSHOC repositories*.

(b) expected developments by the end of the project

Distributing information on the SSHOC Marketplace curation process to different data communities will be a priority. Training materials are important building blocks of the SSHOC Open Marketplace and will be further interlinked with tools, services and data, to contextualise these assets to SSH scholars.

The activities of promoting data stewardship and active inclusion of data stewards will continue. Also, the forthcoming report on TDR status and certification solutions for SSHOC repositories will include the topic of data stewardship, especially from the viewpoint of long-term preservation of data. *League of Data* platform will be designed and promoted, gamifying Data Management Expert Guide tool, which can help data stewards working with social science data.

(c) recommendations on follow-up priorities linked to the further development of EOSC

Support long-term data stewardship and data management in trusted repositories. As the SSH work continues to be included in the EOSC, fragmentation of the landscape remains one of the challenges of long-term data stewardship. Participation in innovative projects using new technologies and approaches that require data resources from different domains should be stimulated. Digital data and associated metadata maintained in a readable and usable form should be associated with repositories committed to the preservation and open dissemination of this data, thus supporting the goals of the SSH community and facilitating participation within EOSC.

Invest in **capacity building for discipline-attuned data stewardship.** More awareness should be raised within the SSH, as well as other scientific domains, regarding the role and relevance of 'data stewards' and 'data stewardship' processes. Future policy should provide clear mechanisms and strategies to increase this awareness, including funding schemes to train data stewards within research organisations, as well as provide continued and long-term support for the creation of pan-European guidelines for data stewardship then cascaded to the various national-level research-funding and research-promoting bodies.

5. Cross-cluster collaboration

(a) main results achieved so far

The SSHOC consortium has proven that research infrastructures from the SSH domain can jointly provide a valuable service offer, with use cases within the social sciences and humanities and with potential for impact in other domains.

The coordinators of the five INFRA EOSC-04 cluster projects have been meeting bi-weekly since 2020. Their strategic alignment has resulted in collaboration on two position papers on ESFRI clusters: Position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC (2020), and ESFRI Science Clusters Position Statement on Expectations and Long-Term Commitment in Open Science (2021) as well as an organised workshop “ESFRI science clusters’ long term commitments to Open Science” held on 11th June 2021 .

The latter was jointly presented to the wider community in the stakeholder engagement event [ESFRI Science Clusters’ Long Term Commitments to Open Science](#)¹. The last joint statement was the response to the EOSC Association’s consultation on the new HE RI work programme for funding period 2023-2024.

Other initiatives aiming at alignment of efforts in different areas have been ongoing since 2019:

- ➔ Two cross-cluster events where representatives of the five cluster projects discussed commonalities and collaboration of the EOSC cluster projects in community research data management solutions, thematic data services, connecting to end-user communities, and governance: [EOSC Services, Collaborations and RDA at RDAP14](#) , and [The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of Commons Report at RDA VP17](#).
- ➔ [Realising EOSC conference](#) as a joint activity of SSHOC, FREYA, and EOSC-Hub promoted and supported the integration of different stakeholder communities in the realisation of SSH in EOSC, covering cross-cluster topics such as sustainability, citizen science, onboarding to EOSC, and thematic marketplaces. The conference included an exposition of 33 EOSC projects.
- ➔ Participation in RDA groups to discuss with experts from other disciplines and regions.
- ➔ Participation in metadata catalogue integration work initiated by FAIRsFAIR.

➔ SSHOC Marketplace efforts in collaboration with other cluster cataloguing initiatives.

➔ Training efforts across clusters and OpenAIRE. To this end, interaction has been established between the [SSH Training Community](#) and the [OpenAIRE CoP for training coordinators](#). The [SSH Trainers Directory](#) offers visibility of the trainers not only in the SSH, but also to other domains.

(b) expected developments by the end of the project

SSHOC will continue interdisciplinary workflow creation in the SSHOC Marketplace. The SSH Training Community sustainability scenarios include the potential integration under the CoP for training coordinators, but also the uptake from one of the ERICs.

Strategic coordination meetings will continue and initiatives for more formalised collaboration have been communicated to the EC and REA. A series of use cases is being prepared, aiming at research agendas for the study of political manifests, migration, public debates in times of COVID-19, etc.

(c) recommendations on follow-up priorities linked to the further development of EOSC

Actively use the unique position of the Science Clusters between the EOSC and research infrastructures to connect the EOSC with research infrastructures and provide communication channels with end-users.

Ensure **continued collaboration between the Science Clusters** as a key precondition for the emergence of a landscape that enables and supports collaboration across disciplinary boundaries. Addressing complex societal issues such as climate change, pandemics, social injustice, migration, and multilinguality requires a coordinated, multifaceted approach.

Actively **support the development of multidisciplinary research agendas** which require innovative methodologies for the handling of heterogeneous datasets rooted in multiple domains. This will continue to call for joint work by data science experts and infrastructural support that is informed by disciplinary dynamics complementing the expertise on generic service provision and data handling practice.

1 <https://indico.in2p3.fr/event/24327/timetable/?print=1&view=standard>

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